

Lower Crossed Syndrome (LSD)

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Abstract

The article presents the Lower Crossed Syndrome, which is an increasing problem among the current population. There were fully depict the causes leading to the limitation of the mobility of the lumbar-sacral-pelvic complex and the consequences that it entails. There were mentioned symptoms about postural changes that are the basis for the diagnosis of this syndrome. There were also indicated the process of disturbed biomechanics of excessive tension of several muscles and as well as pathological weakness of others. As well ailments experienced by patients, which are the result of serious consequences and compensation in the human body were included. The article also contains the process of treatment. There were described exemplary techniques used by physiotherapists and workout exercises that are both an element of rehabilitation and prophylaxis.

Keywords: Lower Crossed Syndrome, therapy, prophylaxis.

1. Introduction

Lower Crossed Syndrome is a postural disease, resulting from myofascial disbalance near the lumbar section of the spine and the pelvis rim. This syndrome is characterized by increased lumbar lordosis and front inclination of pelvic, which carries a number of postural changes at other levels of the body and pain or stiffness caused by limitation of the mobility of the lumbar-sacral-pelvic complex. The name of the syndrome comes from the fact that the contorted muscles of the lower back are crossed with the contorted flexors of the hip joint and similarly weakened abdominal muscles cross with the stretched gluteal muscles (figure 1).

The occurrence of this disease grows every year, and this is caused by a change in the lifestyle of a people from active to sitting. Evolution did not adapt people to sit for many hours during the day, but to use the vertical posture as much as possible. The cause of myofascial imbalance is the disturbance of muscle tension and structural homeostasis, which consists in the increased work of tonic muscles and weakened (inhibited) work of the phase muscles as a result of the body's posture that is still being taken incorrect. The Central Nervous System, which adapts the control over the coordination of muscles in the changed functional range, has its role in preserving the wrong movement pattern. From a given description, it could have seemed that this syndrome can only affect people who lead an mostly sedentary lifestyle. Unfortunately, this is not the rule, and this dysfunction is affect not only people sitting for most of the day, but also those who spend half the day sitting, or even those who care about regular movement, as well professional athletes. It is caused by perpetual incorrect posture taken during everyday activities and exercises performed using an incorrect technique that disturbs proper movement patterns. Another aspect of this problem is the fact that

even people who care about workout do not devote enough time for training central stabilization and exercises correcting the vertical posture of the body and correct positioning of the pelvis or they don't doing it at all. [1; 2]

Figure 1. Schematically presented problem of muscular disbalance within the pelvic-lumbar complex forming a characteristic X [3].

Diagnosis of postural disorders syndrome included in the title is not complicated. Following symptoms such as:

- front inclination of pelvic
- lumbar hyperlordosis,
- lower limb set in external rotation,

they are visible very clearly, make the person's attitude resembling a duck posture (Figure 2) and the symptoms felt by the patient, i.e. pain of the lower part of the spine

and stiffness make up the recognition Lower Crossed Syndrome. The position characteristic for this syndrome is caused by the shortening of one muscle group, with simultaneous stretching and weakening of the others muscles. So the biomechanics of this disbalance presents in a huge simplification.

Figure.2. Setup of the pelvis in the front inclination, characteristic for the Lower Crossed Syndrome, create the look of duck posture.

A more comprehensive view of this problem, considering the anatomy of the muscles, shows that:

- Some muscles are excessively tense (shortened, tonic):
 - iliopsoas
 - rectus femoris
 - sartorius
 - tensorfasciae latae
 - quadratus lumborum
 - erector spinae (lower part of back)
 - piriformis.
- Some muscles are weakened (inhibited, stretched, phased):
 - gluteus maximus
 - rectus abdominis (especially the lower part),
 - transverse abdominal.

In order to diagnose muscular tone of the above-mentioned muscles, the examination by touch is very useful. There is no need talented physiotherapist to palpatory diagnose whether the muscles are too tense or relaxed. In addition to visual assessment and direct physical contact with the patient, diagnostic tests for muscle length are also recommended (eg Thomas' test, Janda's differentiating or thigh muscle test), muscle strength tests by Lovett's scale or simply measure the

ranges of movements in the joints using the goniometer [4].

3.The after-effects

What is the Lower Crossed Syndrome apart from being a postural syndrome, visible at first glance? In fact, it is the reason of many serious consequences and compensations in the human body, which often lead to pain or overload. The consequences of the absence of muscle homeostasis at the level of the lower limb hoop have a huge impact on biomechanics not only the hip joints, but also the knee, ankle, shoulder and vane joints, and above all the spine joints. Pathological worsening of the lumbar lordosis causes worsening of the cervical lordosis, increase of thoracic kyphosis and wrong setting of the sacrum bone. Incorrectly positioned sacrum bone affects the pelvis through the iliosacral joints, where often in the case of this joint, the surface of the sacrum and hip bone is blocked. Lumbar hyperlordosis leads to a conflict of spious processes, blockages of spinal segments and limitation of mobility in each plane. Often, this syndrome causes radicular symptoms that are confused with the compression of nerve structures or dysfunctions of the intervertebral discs. Excessively tensed back muscles lead to metabolic disorders within the spine, which results in fibrosis or calcifications within the spine segments. In addition, hydration of the intervertebral discs deteriorates. The problem of "disks" dehydration can not be neglected, because it reduces the cushioning capacity of the spine and thus increases the risk of damage in the form of hernias. A contorted hip flexor muscle group limits the extension of the hip joint, which compensates for the lumbar section with each movement, which is overexploited in this case. Ailments in the form of pain and discomfort due to stiffness can directly lead to too strong muscle tension. A series of axial backbone compensations causes the transfer of the center of gravity, which translates into the change of force and force vectors acting on eg hocks or knees joints, which in turn causes incorrect loading of these very important joints and as consequently overload pain of these structures. In such cases, patients often look for a problem directly in the place of pain, for example in the knee, instead of in disturbed biomechanics caused by pelvic stiffness pathologies. The next negative aspect of this ailment is unattractive hunched silhouette with unnaturally fastened buttocks forming the image of a sick and unhealthy person [5; 6; 7].

4. Treatment and prevention

As we already know from the previous chapter, untreated Lower Crossed Syndrome causes many restrictive consequences within the human movement apparatus. Muscle disbalance negatively affects the biomechanics of the spine and peripheral joints. In the case of this syndrome, the pathologies in the myofascial system are good prognosis in treatment, but on condition

that bone structures remain intact. Lower Crossed Syndrome therapy aims to normalize the tension of muscles affected by dysfunction. Excessively tense and shortened muscles should first be relaxed and then stretched. The situation is reversed in the case of phase muscles, which are weakened and stretched, therapeutic treatment consists in activating this muscle group and restoring the proper muscular tonus. In order to achieve relaxation of the myofascial apparatus, physiotherapists use many types of techniques to affect tissue such as trigger point therapy, postisometric muscle relaxation, classic massage, deep tissue massage or various fascial techniques. In turn, to activate and strengthen the muscles that are stretched and weakened, many types of exercises are used, such as isometric exercises, active exercises or active exercises with pushback. A very important part of rehabilitation and, as a consequence, recovery is educating the patient to reduce the time spent in a bad position and changed the movement patterns of the basic activities of everyday life. It is equally important to change the motor habits and devote some time to training aimed at improving the mobility and the condition of the structures of the lumbo-sacral-pelvic complex. The work performed by the patient at home plays a huge role in both treatment and prophylaxis. The right set of exercises arranged by the physiotherapist will speed up the return to physical fitness and ensure to no return to the problem, the only condition is solid and systematic work. [8; 9; 10]

5. Summary

Lower Crossed Syndrome is very common in today's world, caused by sedentary lifestyle and neglecting the correct muscular balance within the lumbar-pelvis complex. It is an extremely common and at the same time underestimate problem that has adverse consequences in human kinematic chains. Observing people moving around in the streets, there is no need for research or statistics to notice that it applies to practically everyone, only at different stages of advancement the syndrome. The proposed methods of treatment and prophylaxis bring fully satisfying effects. However, it can be assumed that causes such as lack of awareness about the disease in the current population and a sedentary lifestyle constitute the basis for supposing the problem will affect an increasing number of people [11].

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Conflict of interest:

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